

$\log K_1^H$ was obtained as Bjerrum half integral value method⁷. The same has been calculated by pointwise calculation method, at different points using the following equation :

$$\log P_{K_1}^H = pH + \log \frac{H\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}_H}$$

The complex ligand formation curve was then obtained by plotting degree of formation of the complex (\bar{n}) against negative logarithm of the concentration of non-protonated ligand (pL) using the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰. For the determination of metal-ligand stability constants, Bjerrum half integral method was used. In addition, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were obtained by pointwise calculation method using the following equations :

$$\log K_1 = pL - \log \frac{1-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}}$$

$$\log K_2 = pL - \log \frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}-1}$$

The value of \bar{n} obtained are of the order 2 between pH range 6.5-8.0. This suggests that Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} form two types of complexes in the proportion 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 with tyrosine (Table 1).

Table. 1. VALUES OF THE PROTONATION CONSTANT and STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES AT 35°.

Cation	Constants	$\mu = 0.1$	$\mu = 0.2$	$\mu = 0.3$
	$\log K_1^H$ (amino functional group)	9.20	9.18	9.15
Pr^{3+}	$\log K_1$	4.68	4.60	4.53
	$\log K_2$	4.12	4.10	4.09
	$\log \beta_2$	8.80	8.71	8.62
Nd^{3+}	$\log K_1$	4.54	4.47	4.40
	$\log K_2$	4.01	3.96	3.91
	$\log \beta_2$	8.55	8.43	8.31
Sm^{3+}	$\log K_1$	4.91	4.85	4.79
	$\log K_2$	4.38	4.30	4.22
	$\log \beta_2$	9.29	9.15	9.01

Most of the amino acids are present as single protonated form HL in the pH range 2.7 to 8.5. A few amino acids occur as H_2L , H_2L^+ form over the whole range. This is true for tyrosine where protons of phenolic group are not released. The comparison of metal-ligand stability constant values of tyrosine with those of serine permits the conclusion that unionised hydroxyl group is not participating in complex formation^{8,11}. The coordination appears to be only through amino nitrogen and carboxylic oxygen. The difference in $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} with tyrosine is less than 1.5, indicating the simultaneous formation of two types of complexes. The values of log step formation constant at various ionic strengths, extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave step thermodynamic formation constants¹⁰. Likewise the values of overall

thermodynamic stability were obtained and symbolised as experimental $\log \beta_2^{\mu=0}$ (Table-2). The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ decreases with an increase in ionic strength¹². The order of overall stability of these complexes is $Sm^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Pr^{3+}$ as expected from their electronic configuration.

Table 2. VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS

	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Sm^{3+}
$\log K_1^{\mu=0}$	4.75	4.61	4.97
$\log K_2^{\mu=0}$	4.14	4.16	4.44
$\log \beta_2^{\mu=0}$ (experimental)	8.89	8.77	9.42

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Amine Exchange Reactions of Mixed Imine Schiff base Complexes of Ni(II)

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The amine exchange (transamination) reactions of coordinated salicylideneamine have been investigated by several workers earlier¹⁻⁸. The influence of basicity and concentration⁴⁻⁶ of the amine in the case of transamination reactions have been variously discussed, but no generalization is possible. The preparations of mixed ligand complexes of the type MLL' [Where L=salicylideneamine or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethylethylamine, L' =1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneamine and M=Ni(II)], have been reported earlier⁹⁻¹⁰. In the present investigation, the amine exchange reactions on above complexes have been carried out and the structures of the complexes have been discussed on the basis of experimental data.

Experimental

Material used: Mixed ligand imine complexes [salicylideneamine or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneamine] Ni(II) were prepared as earlier^{9,10}. Methylamine, ethylamine, *n*-propylamine, *iso*-propylamine and *n*-butylamine of (FLUKA) make were used. Acetone, methanol and chloroform were Analar grade reagents.

Amine exchange reactions of mixed imine Schiff base complexes: Alkylamine (5 ml) and salicylideneamine or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneamine Ni(II) com-

The time required for the completion of the reaction in case of Me-NH₂, Et-NH₂, *n*-pr-NH₂, *i*-pr-NH₂ and *n*-Bu-NH₂ were 10 hr., 12hr, 15hr, 16hr, and 16hr, respectively.

The compounds were analysed and subjected to TLC analysis, magnetic, visible and IR spectral studies.

Results and Discussion

On reaction of mixed ligand imine Schiff base complexes of Ni(II) with methylamine, ethylamine, *n*-propylamine, *iso*-propylamine or *n*-butylamine, transamination reaction takes place as follows :

plexes (1 g.) in 50 ml methyl alcohol were refluxed on a water bath for 10 hr. The solution was then filtered and concentrated. The crystals were filtered off and recrystallized from methyl alcohol.

Where, R = -CH₃ (Me), -C₂H₅ (Et), *n*-C₃H₇ (*n*-pr), *i*-C₃H₇ (*i*-pr) or *n*-C₄H₉ (*n*-Bu). The compounds were found to be pure, as shown by TLC analysis and are non conducting.

Table—1. ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS, MAGNETIC MOMENTS and ANALYTICAL DATA OF N-ALKYL MIXED LIGAND SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES OF Ni(II)

No.	Name of the complexes.	ANALYTICAL DATA %				Electronic Spectral Band	Magnetic Moment in B.M.				
		Calculated		Found							
		Ni	C	H	N	Ni	C	H	N		
1.	N-Methyl [Salicylideneaminato 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II).	17.23	59.87	5.28	8.22	16.95	60.00	5.18	8.25	600	2.85
2.	N-Ethyl [Salicylideneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	15.92	61.83	5.99	7.59	15.95	61.60	6.04	7.30	610	2.88
3.	N-Propyl [Salicylideneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	14.80	—	—	7.06	14.93	—	—	6.98	610	2.95
4.	N-Iso-Propyl [Salicylideneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	14.80	63.52	6.55	7.06	14.83	63.12	6.46	6.80	610	2.90
5.	N-Butyl [Salicylideneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	13.82	64.98	7.06	6.95	13.51	65.00	6.98	6.34	610	3.38
6.	N-Methyl [2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	14.91	64.49	5.12	7.16	14.80	64.65	5.25	6.95	570	1.45
7.	N-Ethyl [2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	14.08	—	—	6.71	13.95	—	—	6.65	590	1.93
8.	N-Propyl [2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	13.14	—	—	6.26	13.00	—	—	6.16	580	2.71
9.	N-iso-propyl [2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	13.14	67.15	6.26	6.26	12.98	67.00	6.38	6.02	580	2.95
10.	N-Butyl [2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneaminato, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylideneaminato] Ni(II)	12.36	68.25	6.74	5.89	12.25	68.45	6.85	5.72	590	3.02

NOTES

The present investigation shows that the amine-exchange reaction can occur with good yield when the reacting amine is more basic than the liberated amine^{4,6}. Alkylamines being more basic than ammonia can replace it easily. The rate of amine exchange reaction is dependent on the relative bulk of the incoming and outgoing amines. Rate of reaction is slow in case of propyl and *iso*-propyl amines.

The IR spectra of mixed-imine Schiff base complexes of nickel show a -N-H stretching frequency at 3300 cm⁻¹. The disappearance of the 3300 cm⁻¹ band after amine exchange reaction can be attributed to the replacement of the N-H hydrogen in nickel mixed imine Schiff base complexes by an alkyl group.

Ni(II) square planar complexes are expected to be diamagnetic. The Ni(II) complexes, however, exhibit paramagnetism ($\mu = 2.8$ to 3.4 B.M.). This can be attributed to polymerization leading to distorted octahedral structure¹¹⁻¹⁴.

The visible spectra of Ni(II) paramagnetic complexes show a shoulder at 610 to 630 nm ($\epsilon = 50$ to 80). There are no bands at higher wavelength region showing square planar structure. The reflectance spectra of the complexes have also been obtained. They exhibit rise in optical density beyond 900 nm indicating distorted octahedral structure. This supports polymerization in the solid state. In solution the polymerization breaks, resulting in the square planar structure.

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Mechanism of Electroreduction of Nickel(II) Complexes

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In the *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 1976 ; 14A, 410, H. S. Sharma and H. L. Nigam have published a paper entitled "Correlation of spectral and redox properties of some nickel(II) complexes of thiomalic acid and thiovanol" in which the authors have proposed a mechanism of electron transfer for the electro-reduction of the nickel(II) complexes which is identical to what had been proposed earlier¹ based on studies on some nickel(II) complexes, which was in fact an extension of the ideas based on earlier studies on some copper(II) complexes². Subsequently on the basis of studies on several nickel(II) complexes of different charge type (cationic, non-ionic and anionic) a more refined mechanism has been suggested³. This correlates well the ease of electron transfer with the ligand field splitting parameter for a series of nickel(II) complexes of a particular charge type, i.e. enables a general correlation of the spectral and redox properties of these complexes.

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